

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

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Report on **Milestone 19**

Consultation with SSH data producers

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Milestone	31/06/2019 (M6)
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Work Package	WP4 - Innovations in Data Production
Task	4.7 Task 4.7 Modeling the SSHOC data life cycle
Version	V1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.12

Abstract:

This text concerns the achievement of the MS19 “Consultation with SSH data producers completed”. SSHOCro will be a common meta level schema to be used as top level ontology for organizing knowledge and information found distributed across various resources of data in the SSH open cloud. This will be achieved by providing a common, agreed –upon, understanding of the concepts, entities and relationships holding between them, in order to enable knowledge sharing, information exchange and integration between heterogeneous sources. MS19 ensures that said concepts, entities and relationships can be addressed by means of considering research workflows from the social sciences and humanities.

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Author List

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1. Introduction

The implementation of the **SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro)** should be based on the following principles in order to provide a functional semantic interoperability framework for the description of the SSHOC data life cycle.

Scientific data cannot be understood without knowledge on the meaning of the data and the ways and circumstances of their creation. This knowledge comprises the provenance of the data. According to the W3C Provenance Incubator Group “Provenance of a resource is a record that describes entities and processes involved in producing and delivering or otherwise influencing that resource.”¹

Scientific data can be synthetic, such as simulation data, but mostly they are based on results from observation, in particular on measurements by devices creating digital output. Generally, we use metadata to assess meaning (the recorded things, experimental setup, instrument used, and parameter setting), relevance (status, conditions of the recording and derived information), quality (calibration, tolerances, measurement errors, processing artifacts and error propagation) and possibilities of improvement and data reprocessing.

The key to provenance metadata is the description of processes starting at the level of human activities or actions, which in turn, among others, initiate “machine events” on devices and computers and form a connected graph through the data and things involved in multiple events in roles such as input and output.

The relevant context of these actions comprises descriptions of objects, people, places, times which, in turn, may be related to other things.

To this end, FORTH organized a workshop to consult with partners from the SSH scientific community who produce and process data.

¹ W3C Provenance Incubator Group. <http://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/prov/wiki/>.

2. Description of the Milestone

The workshop aimed to identify representative, high level research workflows and their interaction within the data lifecycle: what tools and services are used by the different research communities at what point in the data life cycle, what data is generated and when, how is it corrected, who uses it, what standard data sources are commonly integrated, where is data sought, where is it archived and under what conditions etc. By identifying the sets of tools, services and data used by researchers on the one hand, their respective ends and order of application on the other, tried to set the basic empirical foundations for building a first iteration of a conceptual model we will set the basic empirical foundations for building a first iteration of a conceptual model. While the tools, services and data standards adopted by different communities within SSH will differ significantly, by identifying the basic workflows that exist, we will be able to begin defining common features and relations, in order to establish the general conceptual model.

The workshop was held at Heraklion, Crete, 20-22 May 2019 and all interested partners from the SSH scientific community were invited to participate.

Also, a brief questionnaire [appendix A] was shared among the work package leaders of the project for getting a preliminary idea on the services, methods and standards used by researchers in the SSH community. The answers on this questionnaire may be found in appendix B.

2.1. Role of the Milestone

The role of the milestone was to discuss with representatives of social science & humanities researches in order to identify sets of tools, services and data used by researchers on the one hand, their respective ends and order of application on the other, for setting the basic empirical foundations for building a first iteration of a conceptual model.

Through the discussion, we expected to be informed with high level research workflows and their interaction within the data lifecycle. The conclusions of the discussion contributed to a deeper understanding of the requirements of research infrastructures to support an actual knowledge ecosystem of scientific research interaction. Also, it is proved that the deeper study of the following workflows mentioned in 3 is sufficient for identifying overlapping / common or hidden concepts, patterns and relationships, and synthesizing those into more generic concepts and relationships that might apply to other workflows beyond the domain of the initial ones.

2.2. Means of verification

The presentations of the workshop are the results of consultation according the description of MS19 (for an overview of the presentations –with hyperlinks –the reader is referred to the [minutes of the workshop](#) (Stored in SSHOC Document repository).

3. Conclusions and next steps

Based on the presentations and the conclusion of the discussion, it was decided that the next steps in T4.7 should involve collecting workflows of:

1. digital edition & NLP processing (Matej Durco, ACD-OEAW)
2. analytic techniques in conservation methods (Joe Padfield, NG)
3. Social science surveys (Slava Tykhonov, KNAW-DANS)
4. Biology research (Chryssoula Bekiari, FORTH-ICS)
5. 3D Coform (Maria Theodoridou, FORTH-ICS)
6. Sealit (Martin Doerr, FORTH-ICS)
7. Aioli (Ariane Neroulidis, CNRS-MAP)

4. List of appendixes

Appendix A: [Questionnaire](#)

Appendix B: [Answers of the questionnaire on SSH data metadata, methods and tools Task 4.7](#)

Appendix C: [An example of historical research](#)

Appendix D: [An example of Natural Language Processing](#)

Appendix A – Questionnaire

WP4 - Innovations in Data Production

Task 4.7 Modeling the SSHOC data life cycle

Task 4.7 aims at defining a common metalevel schema, the **SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro)**, to provide a semantic interoperability framework for the description of the SSHOC data life cycle.

To this end, FORTH plans to organize a workshop to consult with partners from the SSH scientific community who produce and process data. The workshop will aim to identify the sets of metadata commonly used across the scientific communities comprising the SSH domain through a comparison of the services, the methods and standards used by each respective community. These sets of metadata may refer to diverse content/concepts and context, may embody similar concepts expressed with different terms, may partially overlap, etc. However, all these diversities have to be considered and at the end connected up to the common **SSHOCro** metalevel schema/ontology.

FORTH proposes the workshop to take place in Heraklion, Crete, in the week 27-31 May 2019 and cordially invites all interested partners from the SSH scientific community to participate.

The following brief questionnaire will help us get a preliminary idea on the services, methods and standards used by researchers in the SSH community and we kindly ask all partners to fill it in and return it to FORTH to Sophia Sotiropoulou (sophiaso@iesl.forth.gr) and Eleni Tsoulouha (tsoulouha@ics.forth.gr) by 31 March 2019.

Questionnaire on SSH data/metadata, methods and tools

1. What is your domain/field of expertise? (cultural heritage studies, economy, education, election studies, gender studies, history, language and humanities, law, migration and mobility studies, political science, sociology, other²)
2. What kind of research questions do you address in your current research?
3. What methods/protocols do you consider while collecting/generating data?
4. What kind of (software) tools do you make use of in collecting/generating data?
5. Please specify the type of data that you collect/produce in your research.
6. Please specify the formats of data that you produce in your research

² This list is by no means exhaustive

7. Do you make use of metadata standards in the production of your data? If so, which?
8. Do you make use of vocabularies/thesauri in the production of data? If so, which?
9. What tools do you make use of while processing data?
10. What methods/protocols do you consider while processing data?
11. Do you have any sample data that you could share, to be used/consulted in the course of the project?
12. Do you adopt a data management plan? Does it follow a particular standard?
13. Do you archive your data? If so, where?
14. Do you publish your data? If so, where? If not, please specify why.
15. Which kinds of user use your data? (discipline)
16. Where do people find your data?

Contact Person details	
Name:	
Institution:	
Email:	
Skype-ID:	

For more information regarding this questionnaire, please contact Dr. Sophia Sotiropoulou (sophiaso@iesl.forth.gr) and Eleni Tsoulouha (tsoulouha@ics.forth.gr).

Appendix B - Answers of the questionnaire on SSH data metadata, methods and tools Task 4.7

Timestamp	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20		
3/22/2019 14:16:36	Cultural heritage studies	Using archaeological data and methods to find out about the human past	Standard archaeological methods and protocols eg professional standards for fieldwork and data collection	Spreadsheets, databases, GIS, 2D and 3D digital imaging.	Archaeological fieldwork and desk-based study	Text files; structured data (e.g. in spreadsheets); CAD files; GIS shape files; RTI data; X ray imaging	Archeology Data Service (Guides to Good Practice http://guides.archaeologydata-service.ac.uk/ggp/)	Extensive usage of MIDAS Heritage data standards: https://www.heritagedata.org/home/	GIS; CAD; spreadsheets; databases; RTI viewers	Discipline-specific methods	Yes. Most is archived on ADS	Yes. Dependent upon funder, but broadly follows DCC guidelines https://archaeologydata-service.ac.uk/	https://archaeologydata-service.ac.uk/	Archeology	Metadata on archived data are published in FSD's data portal https://services.fsd.uta.fi/catalogue/research/?lang=en , and in national catalogues and in CESSDA catalogue. Data are available according to specific access conditions.	Metadata on archived data are published in FSD's data portal https://services.fsd.uta.fi/catalogue/research/?lang=en , and in national catalogues and in CESSDA catalogue. Data are available according to specific access conditions.	Archaeology	Where do people find your data? (if applicable)	Your Name	Institution	E-mail	Skype ID
3/25/2019 10:30:39 3/27/2019 13:33:37	Other Language	I work in a data archive and thus don't do research.	I don't collect/generate data.	I don't collect/generate data.	I don't collect/generate data.	I don't do research. At the data archive, quantitative data are mainly in SPSS portable format, but also can be used. Qualitative data are mainly textual.	All data are described using DDI Codebook metadata. Archival Information Packages include also METS and PREMIS metadata.		SPSS and in-house scripts		All archived data are available: https://services.fsd.uta.fi/catalogue/research/?lang=en	FSD is a data archive.		Mainly social scientists but users come from a wide range of disciplines, and also from outside academia.	Metadata on archived data are published in FSD's data portal https://services.fsd.uta.fi/catalogue/research/?lang=en , and in national catalogues and in CESSDA catalogue.		Finnish Social Science Data Archive, Tampere University	marl.kleemola@utu.fi	marl.fsd			
3/29/2019 16:20:02	Cultural heritage studies	Most of my research is generally applied and related to how things can actually be done on a day to day level. How can we make this easier? How can we describe what we have done efficiently and consistently? How can we present this clearly? How can we use technology to make the varied, complex, job of studying and caring for cultural heritage easier, more efficient and more accessible?	Conservation science uses a very wide range of techniques, but all come with their own methods and protocols, so it is hard to name any specifics. But in general they are based on agreed standards where possible, but often tailored to the domain specific requirements.	Quite a wide range of books. When connected to specific pieces of equipment bespoke and commercial software if often required. Where possible, I also create bespoke software for many smaller applications.	We work with most types of data, text, numbers, 2D & 3D images, 2D & 3D data arrays, point measurements, video & audio. Generally the data is collected in controlled lab or studio environments, but various projects have involved external and potentially public subjects. In some cases time is also a factor so repeat measurements are made over time.	Over time we can consider almost every common data format and many more dedicated or bespoke formats.	Metadata standards or community conventions exist for several of the techniques we use and they are followed where possible. We do concentrate on ensuring that all gathered data can be linked back to the objects being studied and connected to other related activities.	Yes, we have used and created several among different projects but do try to connect things back to some of the larger public options where possible. Such as the Getty Vocabularies and linked to other related activities.	Many of the project I have been involved in have involved one of or plot examinations, so the software has often been written in house. But we have recently experimented with the Termines, Profigit, 3M and Google Refine. I have used python, php and perl to create bespoke tools in the past.	In most of the recent semantic data processing projects we have been aiming to map our data to the CIDOC CRM, considering the growing number of examples carried out in other projects. For the presentation of images we have also been working with IIF for some time.	Within the SSHOC project we will be processing all of the data held within the https://roma.ng-london.org.uk/doi/communitat/ system, there is an XML of the data at the moment but it has not been specifically licensed for re-use, we are hoping to be released under CC BY ND 4.0. We will be mapping it all to the CIDOC CRM in SSHOC	Specific DMPs are adopted for larger scale projects, but we do not follow any specific standard for day to day activities. In general all of our data generating processes follow an internal method and all of the data is stored on our own network, which is backed up, with offsite copies.	We have published data for a number of smaller projects but not as a matter of course. Appropriate processes to publish more of our data are being considered as part of the EURIS EU project.	Quite a wide range of people have used it is the past including: Heritage Scientists, Material Scientists, Digital Humanists, Art Historians, Artists, Software developers, Image Processing Specialists, and many more.	Access to our archives is currently possible via http://www.petercook.eu/archib/ but we do present some domain specific data publicly such as https://research.ng-london.org.uk/projects/ or https://research.ng-london.org.uk/scientific/pdf/ . More simple descriptions and images related to our collection are available via beta APIs - https://data.ng-london.org.uk and https://media.ng-london.org.uk	project web app, humanities data repository and zenodo	historians, literature researchers	project web app, humanities data repository and zenodo	Joseph Padfield	The National Gallery	joseph.padfield@ng-london.org.uk	josephpadfield@hotmail.com
4/19/2019 11:13:54	Cultural heritage studies	I don't understand the question.	?	databases, xml editor	text, images	xml, tiff	own vocabulary				not yet, but later yes	yes, no	yes, humanities data repository and zenodo	historians, literature researchers								
4/19/2019 20:37:51	Humanities	Digital Humanities, Diplomatics, Scholarly Edition, Social History, History of Accounting, Semantic Web / Knowledge Engineering	Transcription of manuscripts, manual / automatic formalisation of transcriptions, domain specific knowledge formalisation	XML editors, XML processors, scripting languages, dedicated VREs, Spreadsheet software	Text, structured data	XML, RDF, csv, images	Of course, everything I find fitting (EAD, TEI, CIDOC CRM, LOD, DC, VRA, RUC, RDA, ...)	Of course, everything I find fitting (GND, VIAF, gennames, Getty thesaurus, iconclass, Hsco, wikidata, ...)	Test editor, R, python, XSLT, Cocoon, eXist, InRoadr, libazephr, MS Access, Excel, openrefine	?		gami-uni-graz-at	historians	google								
4/23/2019 12:30:37	Other	Data Science and Machine Learning for Digital Humanities. Based on what features of the text/course can readers determine whose perspective is expressed in a story? In what respects is understanding a text different/similar in fictional compared to non-fictional discourse?	Crawling, Transforming all kinds of digital data	Mainly Python packages	All kinds of data, especially textual data	Tables, graphics, graphs, geotagged, maps, heatmaps, CSVs, databases, etc.	sometimes we use standards as DCM, FOAF, etc.	Available vocabularies and/or taxonomies in the desired knowledge domains, to increase the retrievability of information on textual corpora, named entities finding, etc.	Python packages		Most of the data we are using is open to everyone.	Normally, we use CRISPRM as a general framework for DS tasks	Endpoints - databases, taxonomies, etc.	Mainly researchers, but we intend it to be used by citizen scientists	We hope it be linked to the LOD Cloud, but also try to open the endpoints to be indexed by google. Expect to do some SEO in the future to increase visibility.		Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities (ÖAW -ACDH)	renato.souza@oaw.ac.at	renato.souza	renatoschouza		
5/17/2019 0:47:55	Language		quantitative methods, speaker preference judgements	Qualities	mainly categorical data, speaker preference judgements	csv, excel	no, I don't use metadata standards	no, I don't use any thesauri	excel, RStudio		possibly yes	no, I don't use a data management plan	at my university's storage disc	I have not published them yet, but I am planning to in scientific journals, and also present them in conferences	my data are saved at my university's storage disc		Sofia Bimpikou	University of Groningen	s.bimpikou@rug.nl			

Appendix C - An example of historical research

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Research Data Life Cycle Session

Task 4.7 an example of historical research

Athina Kritsotaki
31/5/2019

SSHOC, "Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, grant agreement # 823782.

Overview of the Research Process

At its core, all scientific research is an iterative process of

- observation,
- rationalization, and
- validation.

Bhattacharjee, Anol, "Social Science Research: Principles, Methods, and Practices" (2012). Textbooks Collection. 3.
http://scholarcommons.usf.edu/oa_textbooks/3

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SeaLit example: The historian wants to know if there was "a career evolution of ship sailors in Mediterranean Sea in 19th century" continued

Appendix D - An example of Natural Language Processing

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Research Data Life Cycle Session

Task 4.7 an example of Natural Language Processing

Eleni Tsouloucha, ICS FORTH
31/5/2019

SSHOC, "Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, grant agreement # 823782.

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- *observation,*
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    graph TD
      subgraph EXPLORATION
        RQ[Research Questions] --> LR[Literature Review] --> T[Theory]
      end
      subgraph RESEARCH_DESIGN
        O[Operationalization] --> RM[Research Method] --> SS[Sampling Strategy]
      end
      subgraph RESEARCH_EXECUTION
        PT[Pilot Testing] --> DC[Data Collection] --> DA[Data Analysis]
      end
      RQ --> RP[Research Proposal]
      LR --> RP
      LR --> RM
      LR --> SS
      RP --> PT
      PT --> DC
      DC --> DA
      DA --> RR[Research Report]
      RR --> RQ
      RR --> LR
      RR --> RM
      RR --> SS
      RR --> PT
      RR --> DC
      RR --> DA
  
```

Form of a hypothesis to perform an observation
(select parameters, properties, signals and the way of converting these to data)

- Perform the observations. (They are only concerned with objects or events that are observable, either directly or indirectly)
- Explain the observations made and the gathering of data (processing)
- Draw conclusions based upon this data, (make a scientific hypothesis - tentative explanations about the observations made)
- Deduce the implications (test them through further observation, compare the results)
- Confirm, deny, re-evaluate the original hypothesis

Formulate valid theories (allow others to repeat the observations)

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